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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 4

Pages: 359-367

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2672

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14260378

Manuscript Accepted: 11-21-2024

Biochemical Insights into Sugar Consumption and Oral Health Risks with Regards to the Sweet Tooth Effect

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Abstract

This study explores the “Sweet Tooth” effect, focusing on the biochemical implications of sugar consumption on oral health among full-time students and working students at the National University - Mall of Asia (NU-MOA). These groups with demanding schedules face challenges in managing their dietary choices, which may affect their oral health. A survey was conducted with 40 respondents, 20 full-time students, and 20 working students. The researchers compared the group’s sugar consumption habits, dental practices, and awareness of oral health risks associated with high sugar intake. The survey showed that full-time students reported higher consumption of sugary foods and beverages but demonstrated better oral hygiene practices than their working colleagues. However, both groups showed mixed confidence in managing their sugar intake and awareness of its effects on oral health. These results are supported by Prada et al. (2021), where their study showed that college students perceive sugar consumption as both pleasurable and potentially harmful, but are reluctant to change their dietary habits. Moreover, the oral microbiome’s response to sugar, with cariogenic bacteria converting sugars into acids that leads to tooth decay, highlights the risk of high sugar consumption and mediocre oral care practices (Pang et al. 2022). The findings suggest that working students are at a greater risk of having oral health issues due to less frequent dental care. The study highlights the need for targeted dental health education, especially for working students. The researchers suggest further study into stress and other psychological factors contributing to sugar intake is recommended.

Keywords: *Sweet Tooth Effect, working students, full-time students, oral health, oral health risks*

Introduction

The yearning for sweet tastes, which is often referred to as the “sweet tooth” effect, is a universal component of the human experience that is deeply rooted in both our biology and our psyche. This predilection for meals that are high in sugar has its origins in both evolutionary and cultural processes. Sugar-rich foods provide a rapid supply of energy, which has traditionally been advantageous for survival. However, in contemporary diets when sugar is plentiful and readily available, this natural predisposition may lead to health concerns, especially affecting dental health. Sugar may cause a sequence of responses that can be detrimental to dental health, including cavities, tooth decay, and periodontal disease. These reactions are triggered by the biochemical interactions that take place when sugar enters the mouth. These dangers are not only caused by the sugar itself, but also by the intricate relationship that exists between sugar, oral bacteria, and the human biochemical pathways that are responsible for reinforcing the need for sugar.

Sugar has a biochemical interaction with bacteria that are present in the oral cavity, namely *Streptococcus mutans*, which is a key contributor to tooth decay. The pH level in the mouth is lowered as a result of the metabolization of sugar by these bacteria, which results in the production of lactic acid as a byproduct. This acidic environment causes the enamel of teeth to become demineralized, which makes it more difficult to protect against harm. The enamel is worn away over time by the repetitive acid assaults that result from consuming sugar on a regular basis, which ultimately leads to cavities and decay. These dangers are compounded by the sweet tooth effect, which states that the more sugar we ingest, the more so we reinforce our need for more consumption. In the brain, the release of dopamine, a neurotransmitter that is associated with feelings of pleasure and reward, is a major factor in driving this cycle. Dopamine pathways are engaged when we consume meals that are high in sugar, which enhances our desire for sugar and encourages us to consume such foods on a regular basis. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the amount of acid that is produced in the mouth.

Oral health problems connected with a sweet tooth are characterized by a biochemical complexity that is highlighted by the cyclical nature of sugar cravings and intake. The sweet tooth impact is connected to deeper biochemical processes that influence our brain and body, altering our decisions and encouraging behaviors that pose hazards to our dental health. This effect extends beyond basic food habits and is associated with several processes. How the sweet tooth effect affects dental health may be better understood if we have a better grasp of the biochemical systems that are responsible for sugar metabolism in the mouth, as well as the psychological variables that are responsible for sugar intake. It is essential to have such insights in order to design effective measures that may lower the incidence of sugar-induced dental problems, promote oral health, and prevent excessive sugar consumption. The biological and psychological underpinnings of sugar cravings will be investigated in this paper. The article will also investigate how sugar cravings lead to oral health difficulties and what steps may be done to limit the dangers associated with that.

Ubiquitously unhealthy eating and drinking habits and the development of multiple morbidities, including obesity, type-2 diabetes, dental caries and dental erosion have become a major challenge for everyone, mostly students. (Mishra, M., & Mishra, S. (2011)). In recent years, there has been a lot of focus on the connection between sugar intake and dental health, especially within various population segments. This study investigates the phenomenon known as the “Sweet Tooth Effect,” which holds significant relevance in the realm

of dentistry and public health. It examines the correlation between high sugar intake and its detrimental impact on oral health, particularly within two distinct demographics: full-time students and working students of National University-MOA. Due to the students' hectic schedules and lifestyle requirements, these populations frequently encounter distinct obstacles when it comes to food selection and glucose processing, ultimately impacting their oral health negatively. According to Feldens et al. (2022), studies published in the last two decades have shown the negative impact of dental caries on all aspects of life related to oral health, including infancy and an individual's sugar intake. Furthermore, dental caries impacts academic performance, leads to a loss of working hours, and incurs both direct and indirect costs for individuals and society, including a loss of productivity.

This study seeks to shed light on the important connection between sugar intake and risk factors for oral health by analyzing biochemical pathways and dietary habits as well as to offer valuable information on how busy schedules affect biochemical pathways and dietary habits, to guide public health strategies to reduce the harmful effects of sugar on dental health. Specifically, The issue at stake is the rise in dental health problems associated with high sugar consumption among certain population groups, specifically full-time and working students. This study is important because it explains the sweet tooth effect and shows how the distinct lifestyle obstacles experienced by these groups impede their capacity to uphold good oral health

Methodology

This research addresses the biochemical and behavioral components of sugar intake as well as the hazards that sugar consumption poses to oral health among students who are enrolled full-time at National University- Mall of Asia (NU-MOA) and who are also part-time workers. The "sweet tooth" effect, also known as sugar seeking that is mediated by reward pathways in the brain, is especially investigated in this study to determine how it affects these two groups in various ways. The purpose of this research is to shed light on the variables that contribute to oral health risks among students who are dealing with the demands of both their academic and professional lives by evaluating the interplay between dietary habits, biochemical processes in the mouth, and psychological reactions to sugar.

Participant Selection and Grouping

The research sample consists of two distinct groups of students from NU-MOA: those who are enrolled full-time and those who are also working either part-time or full-time in addition to their education. The selection of participants is dependent on their desire to take part in the study, and each participant is asked to fill out a permission form. Participants are recruited via the communication channels of the institution. The two groups provide a comparative perspective on the ways in which different daily routines and levels of stress influence patterns of sugar intake and dental health. In order to collect basic demographic information, lifestyle habits, study and work hours, and dental history, an initial survey is completed by each participant.

Biochemical Analysis of Oral Acid Production

Performing an analysis of the biochemical effects that sugar has on the oral cavity is one of the most important aspects of this research. After each person has consumed a sweet solution that has been standardized, his or her saliva is collected for further analysis. Following this, the samples are tested to determine the variations in pH levels that have occurred over time.

These changes indicate the formation of acid in the mouth as a result of bacterial sugar metabolism. The purpose of this research is to find any changes in acid production that might be correlated with the different patterns of sugar consumption that are experienced by full-time and working students. This will be accomplished by analyzing saliva samples from both groups.

Google Forms served as the primary tool for data collection due to its accessibility and convenience. The survey was distributed to two specific groups of participants: full-time college students and working college students from National University Mall of Asia, all aged between 18 and 25 years. The survey had a total of 40 respondents—20 full-time students and 20 working students. Participants were selected based on their enrollment status, with no restrictions on gender or course of study.

The research procedure commenced with the design of a questionnaire, which included response scale questions. The survey was then distributed via a link and shared through social media platforms to effectively reach the target demographic. An informed consent statement was included at the beginning of the survey, and data collection was managed automatically through Google Forms.

Results and Discussion

The survey was completed by 40 NU-MOA college students. 20 full-time students answered while the other half were answered by part-timer students of NU- MOA.

The survey aimed to understand and compare the habits of sweet consumption, the confidence of individuals to control sugar intake, their dental practices, and the level of awareness of the respondents regarding the implications of sugar on their dental health. Full-time students demonstrated greater sugar consumption and oral health management compared to their working peers.

As shown in Table 1, full-time students reported a greater enjoyment of sweet foods and a higher frequency of consuming and craving sugary snacks and beverages compared to working students.

Table 1. *The sugar consumption of working and full-time students*

Category	Working Students	Full-Time Students
How much do you enjoy sweet foods and beverages?	15%	5%
	“slightly”	“not at all”
	25%	15%
	“somewhat”	“somewhat”
	30%	15%
	“mostly”	“mostly”
	30%	65%
How often do you crave sugary snacks?	“very much”	“very much”
	10%	0%
	“not at all”	“not at all”
	25%	5%
	“slightly”	“slightly”
	20%	40%
	“mostly”	“slightly”
How frequently do you usually eat sweets such as chocolate, cookies, candies, and treats?	25%	20%
	“somewhat”	“mostly”
	20%	35%
	“very much”	“very much”
		10%
		“not at all”
	20%	20%
How frequently do you drink sugary beverages like soda, milk tea, or juice?	“slightly”	“slightly”
	30%	30%
	“somewhat”	“somewhat”
	35%	0%
	“mostly”	“mostly”
	15%	10%
	“very much”	“very much”
		15%
		“not at all”
	30%	5%
	“slightly”	“slightly”
	15%	30%
	“somewhat”	“somewhat”
	40%	30%
	“mostly”	“mostly”
	15%	20%
	“very much”	“very much”

Table 2. *Confidence in maintaining a healthy sugar intake*

Category	Working student	Full-time students
How confident are you that you have a healthy sugar intake for your body?		5%
		“not at all”
	10%	35%
	“Slightly”	“slightly”
	65%	50%
	“somewhat”	“somewhat”
	15%	5%
How often do you feel that sugar consumption affects your oral health?	“mostly”	“mostly”
	10%	5%
	“very much”	“very much”
		20%
		“not at all”
	5%	10%
	“slightly”	“slightly”
How much do you think your sugar consumption affects	15%	35%
	“somewhat”	“somewhat”
	25%	35%
	“mostly”	“mostly”
	20%	
	“very much”	
		10%

your oral health?		“not at all”
	10%	10%
	“slightly”	“slightly”
	30%	40%
	“somewhat”	“somewhat”
	40%	20%
	“mostly”	“mostly”
	20%	20%
	“very much”	“very much”
	How frequently do you manage your sugar intake for the purpose of maintaining dental health?	10%
“inactively monitoring”		“inactively monitoring”
15%		5%
“rarely monitoring”		“rarely monitoring”
40%		50%
“somewhat monitors”		somewhat monitors”
20%		30%
“oftenly monitors”		“oftenly monitors”
15%		10%
“actively monitoring”		“actively monitoring”
How likely are you to change your sugar consumption in the next six months?		5%
	10%	“not at all”
	“slightly”	15%
	35%	“slightly”
	“somewhat”	45%
	30%	“somewhat”
	“mostly”	30%
	25%	“mostly”
	“very much”	5%
	“very much”	“very much”

As shown in Table 2, 65% of the full-time students expressed their confidence in managing their sugar as “somewhat” confident, while working students were feeling average in their confidence.

Table 3. Oral Practices

Category	Working student	Full-time students
How often do you brush your teeth after consuming sugary foods or beverages?	10%	10%
	“immediately after”	immediately after
	15%	35%
	“shortly after”	“shortly after”
	40%	10%
	“later”	“later”
	25%	30%
	“rarely”	“rarely”
	10%	15%
	“never”	“never”
How often do you visit your dentist for routine oral health check-ups?	15%	10%
	“never”	“never”
	20%	5%
	“less than every 2 years”	“less than every 2 years”
	20%	50%
	“once a year”	“once a year”
	35%	25%
	“twice a year”	“twice a year”
	10%	10%
	“more than twice a year”	“more than twice a year”
How effective do you think dietary changes are in improving oral health?	5%	5%
	“slightly”	“slightly”
	40%	15%
	“somewhat”	“somewhat”
	25%	25%
	“mostly”	“mostly”

	30% "very much"	55% "very much"
Table 4. Awareness of sugar's impact on their dental health		
Category	Working student	Full-time students
How would you rate your awareness of the impact of sugar on oral health?	5% "not aware at all"	
	10% "slightly aware"	10% "slightly aware"
	20% "somewhat aware"	15% "somewhat aware"
	25% "aware"	30% "aware"
	40% "very aware"	45% "very aware"

As shown in Table 3 and 4, both groups recognized the impact of sugar on their oral health, however full-time students showed greater awareness, and were proactive in their oral hygiene practices.

The researchers conducted comparative research on Sweet Consumption of the Full-time Student and Working Student in National University MOA.

The study found that full-time students had a persistent preference for sweets, suggesting that they find delight and maybe even comfort in sugary meals and beverages. This pattern was visible in the majority of replies, suggesting that sugar intake among full-time students may be more closely related to leisure, study breaks, or social activities with friends. Their schedules are typically more flexible, making it simpler to include and enjoy sweets into their everyday routines.

However, for working students, the results was less conclusive. Responses indicated an approximately equal distribution of those who "somewhat" like sweets and those who "very much" enjoy them, making it difficult to make clear conclusions about their general preferences. This disparity in replies may indicate that working students' sugar intake is motivated by pragmatism rather than choice. The difficulties of juggling employment and studies may cause working students to resort to sweets as a fast energy source rather than a real delight, resulting in a more varied satisfaction level. Furthermore, time restrictions, work-related stress, or a lack of nutritional options might all contribute to this disparity, since people may value convenience above pleasure in their eating behaviors.

This variation in replies from working students highlights the complexities of their dietary motives. Sweets may be a fast, easy way for some people to stay energized during stressful days, while for others, they may be a pleasure akin to what full-time students enjoy. These variations underline the significance of further investigating the motives for sugar intake among working students in order to better understand how lifestyle variables impact not only their dental health risks, but also their attitudes toward sweet foods.

According to the findings, both working and full-time students had just a slight appetite for sugary snacks. This suggests that, although both groups have a desire to consume sweets, it is not a severe or regular urge. Instead, their interest in sugary treats seems to be modest and situational, rather than motivated by a strong craving for sugar.

This minor demand for sugary snacks in both groups suggests a more balanced approach to sugar consumption, which will likely help prevent possible oral health problems. Students with modest desires are less likely to eat excessive quantities of sweets, which may contribute to dental problems. Instead, their sugar intake seems to be sporadic, motivated by convenience or situational necessities rather than a deep-seated liking or habit for sweet meals.

The study of the third figure indicated a significant difference in food patterns, notably sugar intake, between working and full-time students. Working students had a higher inclination to consume sweets such as chocolate, cookies, candies, and other snacks. This choice shows that working students may depend on these conveniently available, high-sugar foods for a brief burst of energy or comfort during their hectic schedules.

Full-time students seemed to eat sweets less often. The findings reveal that full-time students consume sweets in moderation, as seen by a "somewhat" reaction in their reported intake. This mild inclination might be due to more flexible meal planning times or an emphasis on more balanced meals. It may also represent varying stress levels or lifestyle habits, such as working students having more time limitations and opting for quick snacks vs full-time students having more time to explore alternative options.

The fourth figure shows that sugary drinks are often consumed by both full-time and working students, with many stating that they frequently drink juice, milk tea, and soda. Both groups' consumption patterns of sugary drinks suggest a common predilection or dependence on these drinks, which might provide a short energy boost or a cool respite throughout the day.

Frequent intake of sugary beverages by working students may be a reflection of their desire for easy-to-get energy sources to meet the challenges of juggling employment and school. During hectic workloads, these drinks may give a momentary feeling of refreshment

or alertness due to their quick calorie and sugar consumption. The availability of ready-to-drink sodas or milk teas might make them a desirable choice in settings with little time for breaks.

On the other hand, full-time students could use sugary beverages for a variety of reasons, such as social customs or the need for instant satisfaction in between study sessions. Campus life often promotes getting together over drinks like milk tea or juice, which may turn into a regular feature of their social situations and everyday interactions. These beverages are also popular because to their diversity and marketing, particularly for those who want taste and refreshment without committing to a complete meal.

The results of the study show that while both working and full-time students express only "somewhat" confidence in their health decisions about sugar intake, researchers are unable to definitively ascertain if the respondents' sugar consumption patterns are indeed healthy. This self-reported "somewhat" confidence shows that while students may think they are controlling their sugar consumption to a certain degree, they are not completely certain that their eating habits are healthy.

This modest degree of confidence may indicate that while students are aware of the frequent intake of sugary beverages and sweets, they are unsure about the effects on their general health. Although there may be some worries about the long-term health repercussions, working students may find that relying on fast, energy-boosting foods and drinks is a recognized trade-off for sustaining energy levels. Even while full-time students may believe they have greater control over their decisions, they could still indulge in social or routine sugary treats, which leaves them feeling just "somewhat" secure.

The results show that respondents' impressions of their dental health are significantly impacted by their use of sugar, with full-time students experiencing the effects of sugar on their teeth more severely than working students. 35% of the respondents said they "mostly" noticed how sugar affected their oral health, meaning they were more directly or often aware of sugar-related dental problems such as tooth decay, cavities, or sensitivity.

The increased knowledge of sugar's effects on teeth among full-time students may be related to their eating patterns or surroundings. Full-time students may have more time to think about or identify these health effects, or they may consume sugary foods and drinks in ways that increase their exposure, including snacking or sipping drinks throughout the day, which increases the amount of time sugar comes into contact with their teeth. Because regular sugar consumption encourages the development of acid in the mouth, which progressively erodes tooth enamel, this kind of exposure may raise the risk of dental issues.

According to the survey, a significant percentage of participants—both full-time students and working adults—are aware of the negative consequences that sugar intake has on their dental health, with 40% selecting "mostly" when asked whether they had seen these effects. Students' awareness that sugar consumption has long-term effects on dental health in addition to short-term energy boosts or enjoyment is highlighted by this common worry.

The 40% who selected "mostly" probably suffer from typical dental problems associated with sugar, such as cavities, tooth sensitivity, or enamel erosion. This awareness may result from heightened sensitivity after consumption of sugary foods and beverages or from firsthand experience with oral pain. Despite varying schedules and lifestyle demands, the impacts of sugar on dental health are generally acknowledged across student types, according to the agreement of both full-time and working students.

Working students may require fast, easy snacks that are often heavy in sugar to balance work and study, which over time may have negative effects on their teeth. The social components of drinking sugary beverages and snacks on campus may also contribute to these aftereffects, since full-time students, who may have more time to consider healthy habits, also experience them. The recognition of these side effects by both groups suggests that sugar's influence on dental health is a widespread problem.

This research points to a significant potential for educational initiatives that stress the value of moderation in sugar intake and oral hygiene habits. Students may be able to lessen these impacts and maintain improved oral health if easily accessible information on preventative care is made available. Examples of this information include using fluoride toothpaste, brushing often, and avoiding sugary foods.

According to the research, students who work or attend school full-time "somewhat" control their sugar consumption to preserve their oral health. This suggests that students are making a reasonable effort to learn about the connection between sugar intake and dental health. However, the "somewhat" answer implies that while students may understand the need of reducing sugar intake, their attempts to do so are inconsistent and ineffective.

This moderate approach to sugar control among full-time students may be an effort to strike a compromise between dietary preferences and the demands of college life, where sugary snacks and drinks are often easily accessible and socially acceptable. The availability and simplicity of sugary foods in their surroundings might sometimes compromise their well-meaning attempts to restrict consumption.

Similar to this, working students may be conscious of the need to control their sugar intake for oral health, but they are constrained by hectic schedules that place a premium on instant energy, which often causes them to choose sugary snacks for convenience. Their rigorous schedules might make it difficult for them to regularly follow low-sugar options, which leads to only "somewhat" successful control of their sugar consumption.

The research indicates a lack of significant incentive or urgency to change their dietary habits, since both full-time and working students

are now ambivalent about decreasing their sugar intake over the next six months. This neutrality suggests that while students may have a vague understanding of the negative health impacts linked to consuming large amounts of sugar, they may not now see a strong enough motivation to change their behavior.

This indifferent attitude may be the result of full-time students feeling comfortable with their present routines, either because they don't experience any immediate detrimental impacts or because sugary meals and beverages are ingrained in campus and social life. Being with others who share your use of sugary foods and beverages might normalize these behaviors, making it seem less important to stop.

Sugar's ability to provide them rapid energy boosts amid their hectic schedules may also make working students who are juggling employment and school obligations neutral. Change may not seem like a priority if there is no obvious or immediate advantage to cutting sugar. Convenience often takes precedence over health concerns.

The research finds that when it comes to cleaning their teeth after eating sweet meals, full-time students and working students have different oral hygiene practices. It seems that full-time students respond more quickly to preserving their dental health since they brush "shortly after" ingesting sugary goods. Brushing right away after consuming sugar probably lowers the risk of tooth decay because sugar reacts with oral bacteria to produce acid.

Full-time students may have developed this instant brushing habit because their schedules are more flexible, giving them more opportunity to adopt better hygiene habits. This prompt reaction suggests that full-time students are taking proactive measures to combat sugar's possible negative effects on their teeth.

However, it has been shown that working students brush "later" after eating sugary meals, suggesting a delayed approach to dental hygiene after ingesting sugar. They may not have an immediate chance to wash their teeth because of time restrictions or the hectic nature of their routines. Given that extended exposure to sugary residues may eventually encourage acid accumulation and enamel erosion, this delay may increase their exposure to the negative effects of sugar on dental enamel.

According to the statistics, working students see their dentist twice a year, but full-time students often see their dentist only once. This suggests that different students have different dental checkup frequencies. This discrepancy may be due to differences in the two groups' access, perceptions of the value of dental treatment, or even their financial and temporal resources.

Working students may prioritize preventative dental care more than other students, as seen by their twice-yearly visits. This might be because they are aware of the possible effects of their hectic schedules and food choices on oral health. Frequent check-ups are important for working students because they may help prevent problems caused by sugary foods and beverages, which they may use to get rapid energy boosts during their hectic schedules. Additionally, seeing a dentist every two years can be more convenient for them if their working benefits include dental coverage.

However, full-time students who only see the dentist once a year can indicate that they don't see the need for routine examinations, perhaps because they think that once a year is enough to keep their teeth healthy. Additionally, full-time students could have less time limitations, which might give them greater confidence to maintain good dental hygiene via consistent brushing and other at-home routines. Furthermore, some full-time students choose to forego further expenses by getting the bare minimum suggested yearly checkup because they are financially challenged or do not have dental insurance.

The evidence suggests that full-time students are more aware than working students of the effects of dietary modifications on oral health, and full-time students are more likely to think that dietary changes are "somewhat" helpful for enhancing dental health. This research raises the possibility that full-time students are better aware of the connection between oral health and nutrition or have more time to monitor and consider the results of dietary modifications.

Full-time students may have more time to concentrate on health-related subjects since they usually have more flexible schedules and may feel less stressed overall than their working classmates. This setting may help people become more conscious of the ways that a healthier diet and a lower sugar intake might improve oral health outcomes including decreased plaque accumulation, cavities, and tooth sensitivity. Their awareness of the significance of nutrition in preserving oral health may also be strengthened by increased exposure to health information on campus or from peers.

On the other hand, because of their hectic schedules and limited time, working students could place a higher value on convenience when choosing their meals, giving dietary changes less importance. Even if working students are aware of the overall advantages of eating a better diet, their attention may be diverted from adopting long-term dietary adjustments to enhance dental health by the pressing needs of juggling employment and school. People may not have the time to thoroughly notice or prioritize these impacts, which might explain why people believe that dietary modifications have just a modest, or "somewhat," influence on their dental health.

The research demonstrates that both working and full-time students are aware of how sugar affects oral health, indicating a common grasp of how dietary decisions may affect dental health. This information shows that students are aware of the possible negative effects of eating and drinking sugary foods and drinks, including a higher risk of cavities, gum disease, and enamel erosion.

The educational setting, where full-time students are more likely to come across conversations on nutrition and health via courses, campus health programs, or peer interactions, may be the source of this understanding. Additionally, they could be exposed to dental

hygiene and healthy eating campaigns or seminars that emphasize the link between sugar intake and oral health.

Even though they may have greater time limits and stricter schedules, working students show that they are aware of the harmful consequences sugar has on their teeth. Personal experiences, such as prior oral problems or guidance from dentists during examinations, may give birth to this knowledge. Additionally, as poor dental health may eventually result in more serious health issues, working students may look for knowledge on preserving their health in order to better manage their hectic schedules.

In general, there are distinctions between full-time and working students. Since they consume more, full-time students are more prone to eat sugary meals and drinks, which may have an impact on their dental health. The figures 3 and 11 provide evidence in favor of this theory. Since the data were impartial, figures 7 and 8 contain inconsistencies. However, figures 1 and 3 provide compelling evidence for the idea that full-time students' dental health is more negatively impacted by sweet tooth.

The wider ramifications of this research on students' intake of sweets emphasize the need of focused health initiatives encouraging young individuals to practice good dental hygiene and a balanced diet. Providing routine dental examinations to encourage excellent oral health at colleges and universities. The results may help persuade food and beverage manufacturers to lower sugar levels and provide more healthful alternatives for everybody. By comprehending these elements, we may create plans to enhance young people' public health outcomes.

According to a research by Prada et al. (2021), college students have mixed feelings about sugar intake; they believe it to be both enjoyable and detrimental to their general and dental health. Their study's results closely resemble those of the researcher, who found that full-time and working students of NU-MIOA. The hesitation seen in the thematic analysis of young people in the research by Prada et al. (2021) is reflected in NU-MOA's neutrality against altering their sugar intake over the following six months. Furthermore, university students, who are often going through a big shift, could be more inclined to take control of their oral health habits, establishing them as future leaders and role models in their communities (Peltzer et al., 2017). Research on the variables influencing emerging adults' perceptions of their dental health and oral hygiene practices, especially among Southeast Asian university students, is, however, scarce. Both the incidence of tooth decay and the use of sugary snacks have been linked in studies, as has the relationship between greater stress levels and an increased risk of dental caries.

Consuming sugar might be detrimental to dental health because cariogenic bacteria convert simple sugars into acids that erode teeth (Pang et al., 2022). Too much refined sugar consumption is known to cause cavities. Studies have shown a correlation between sugar consumption and the makeup of mouth bacteria. Increased intake of sugary drinks, for example, might upset children's oral microbiome balance, decreasing microbial diversity and raising the frequency of dangerous bacteria that cause tooth disease.

According to Sogari et al. (2018), students often develop unhealthy eating habits, such as increased alcohol consumption and decreased physical activity, when they go from high school to college or the job. Their eating habits may be impacted by this time of major life transitions. According to research, college is a critical period for young people since it has a big influence on their dietary preferences and may cause weight increase. According to a number of studies, college students usually consume more added sugars, processed meats, and trans fats per day than is advised.

The limitations of this study is that the conclusions may be restricted to all National University MOA students if the population is relatively small. Other related factors concerning sweet consumption and oral health could also have been left out of the scope of study- for instance, the levels of stress, exercises, or access to dental care. Lastly the results may be biased since we conduct a questionnaire type of survey it may not determine enough data that this research needs.

Conclusions

In conclusion, Due to high sugar consumption, this study has shown that both full-time and working students are significantly more likely to experience oral health problems. The results show that acid production from sugar-metabolizing oral bacteria increases sensitivity to dental caries and enamel erosion. While working students tend to have more irregular eating patterns and rely on convenience foods, full-time students benefit from more regular schedules and frequently consume sugary snacks and beverages during study sessions. These two factors all lead to similar hazards to dental health. Because they have busy schedules and less time for good oral care, working students are more vulnerable.

The findings from our study could be used to create specialized dental health education initiatives that cater to these groups' unique requirements. While working students may benefit from time management measures for good oral hygiene, full-time students may benefit from treatments that reduce their consumption of sugary snacks during study periods. More access to reasonably priced dental care services on campuses or through workplace programs would also be beneficial to both groups.

Further research should examine the psychological variables, such as stress and coping strategies, that affect students' consumption of sugar. Additionally, it would be beneficial to look into how well various intervention techniques work to encourage students to adopt improved oral hygiene practices, especially those who are working and have more time constraints. Lastly, prospective studies could evaluate how long- term sugar consumption affects these groups' oral health.

Based on the results and conclusions of the study about sugar consumption and oral health risks among full-time and working students,

The researchers offered the following recommendations:

Long-term studies are a great way to investigate how sugar consumption influences oral health over time. By tracking students for several years, researchers can better understand the ongoing effects of sugar intake on problems like cavities and enamel erosion.

Expand the study to include a variety of demographics and regions. This approach could help uncover valuable insights into how sugar consumption and oral health practices differ among students from various universities and backgrounds, revealing important patterns and disparities.

Future researchers could look into how different sugars affect oral bacteria and contribute to dental issues like cavities. This would help us better understand the biological processes involved.

To propose the study to other researchers to pursue and find out more about health risks of high sugar consumption.

Future research should look into the psychological reasons behind sugar consumption among students, such as stress and emotional eating. Understanding these factors could explain why students, especially those balancing work and studies, often crave sugary foods during stressful periods.

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